

Being Alone with Oneself: Encountering God in Silence

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We always long for a world where we always meet or contact people either at work, in the supply store, on streets or over phones and through social media. In fact, our society tends to label anybody who wants to be or is alone, as isolated or even more drastically as depressed. However, today across the country, also across the world people stare at a drastic experience that no near past can illustrate. The COVID-19 pandemic is radically and rapidly changing our world. The situation is same, irrespective of nationality and religion, richness and poverty, developed or underdeveloped, sophisticated or simple; we are all facing the same thing together, while being apart.

The Silence of Quarantine

We are consumed and confused by hearing diverse opinions of what to do and how to think in the Covid-19 crisis. Perhaps, we are now invited to ponder at an uncommon practice that the Psalmist describes: “For God alone, O my soul, wait in silence, for my hope is from Him” (Ps 62:5). Silence is undoubtedly a forgotten practice in this generation. We have mastered a lot of skills in a world that is

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highly advanced in expertise and techniques, but perhaps have neglected the most important skill of all: the ability to be alone, to learn solitarily, to

understand one’s own strengths and weaknesses, to reflect on life and to appreciate the wonder and the beauty of the nature. Being alone is intentionally deciding to get away from everything and enjoying being with oneself, savouring the beauty of life. We have forgotten how to enjoy our own company. However, today we hear more about the Quarantine, being alone because of the Covid-19 pandemic. Quarantine forces upon a change of plans that we probably won’t like because it limits our mobility and contacts. It confines us to our own homes. It is a recommendation and at the same time an obligation to separate us from the world for the two-fold purposes: to save oneself and to save others from the COVID-19 infection.

Encountering God in Silence

We can know only ourselves when we earnestly look at ourselves in silence. “Be still and know”, says Aristotle. Taking time to be alone is very productive and it can be a wonderful experience. It means to take time away from the social media and friends and finding a suitable place to be with oneself, to relax and analyse our habits and see how they touch our lives. As a believer in God, it is a time to encounter with God in the stillness of our lives. Prophet Elijah, who were to receive God’s message, is a good example (1Kings 19:11). Briefly, there seems to have been a thunderstorm and an earthquake but the Lord was not in either or even in a fire. Then came a still, small

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voice. Elijah covered his face with his cloak and he came out and got the message. Thus, one can find God in stillness and silence. Stillness is more internal and denotes interior peace, tranquillity, restfulness and quietude of mind and heart. It prepares us to be open to the Spirit and thereby receive the Spirit of God. Stillness prepares us for communion and oneness with the Divine. Everything that is broken and distorted has a chance to begin again within us, a chance to bring us back to the source, to the beginning. According to Eckhart Tolle, stillness is timeless inner space on oneself. It is inner most awareness of self.

Silent reflection enables us to wake up to the truth that there is something more to life than what we can see and that there is someone bigger (God) who is real and loves us. This encounter should make a transformation in our lives, especially in our attitude towards others.

God speaks to us in many ways: through the scriptures, nature – the sun and the moon, the rivers and the mountains, birds and animals, our joys and sorrows. Perhaps, His voice is the loudest in silence, in the silence of the desert as the Prophet Elijah testifies. The time of quarantine is a time for us to encounter God in our stillness and the encounter can change our life and attitude. Encounter with God can bring an after effect. We see many examples in the Bible. For instance, Moses, who encounters God in the burning bush (Ex 3: 1-12), had a change in his life. It is a unique personal experience, yet it concerns the whole people. It is the starting point of his mission.

An important step in encountering God in your life is investing time in silence. Silent reflection enables us to wake up to the truth that there is something more to life than what we can see and that there is someone bigger (God) who is real and loves us. This encounter should make a transformation in our lives, especially

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in our attitude towards others. The Christian encounter of God necessarily takes us to our brothers and sisters.

Concluding Challenge

The Covid-19 pandemic astonishes us. Consequently, there are many unanswered questions and apprehensions. We are deeply struck by very tiny, intangible and invisible virus! It is here that we need to instil a positive attitude, a transformation. Amidst this pandemic we can find rays of hope and future. We are close to the celebration of the great feast of resurrection of Jesus where we encounter the risen Christ. In Him we find a new hope and future. In Him we have new life and new order of life. With this trust and hope let us move forward in the midst of this COVID-19 pandemic and experience God, whom we are called to share with our brothers and sisters!

References

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